

CASSAVA COMMODITY OVERVIEW

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Non-oil sector is one source of state revenue in support of the Indonesian economy. Non-oil sector, especially the agricultural sector make a significant contribution to the value of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and the amount of export volume. GDP for the agricultural sector over the last few years shows an upward trend from 2014 until 2016. By looking at the magnitude of the contributions made to the state, the agricultural sector plays an important role as a source of foreign exchange, employment providers, providers of industrial raw materials and provider of food, clothing, and house in Indonesia.

The agricultural sector consists of several sub-sectors, among others: food crops, horticulture, plantation, forestry, animal husbandry and fishery. Food crops consisted of three groups, among others: types of grain crops, legumes and tubers with huge potential to be developed as one of the sources of national income. Commodities tubers such as cassava is one of the food commodities instead of rice a fairly important role in supporting food security and industrial raw material starch territory. Cassava has a higher energy value compared to rice, corn, sweet potato, and sorghum (Widianta and Goddess, 2008). Where cassava contains 60% water, 25-35% starch and protein, minerals, fiber, calcium, and phosphate.

The development of cassava productivity in Indonesia during 1980-2016 tends to increase, along with the increasing passion of farming communities planting cassava varieties superior Elephant. The rate of growth of productivity of cassava in Indonesia increased by an average of 2.64% per annum productivity is 97.51 ku/ha in 1980 to 239.13 ku/ha in 2016. The development of the productivity of the last five years (2011-2016) tended to increase greater than 2.85%, despite a decline in cassava production in 2015 compared to 2014 (Outlook Cassava, 2016).

Cassava production in 2015 as much as 21.80 million tons of wet bulb decreased by 1.63 million tons (6.98%) compared to 2014. Decreasing on cassava production that occurred in Java (East Java, Central Java and West Java) as much as 1.15 million tons and outside Java Island (North Sumatra, South Sulawesi, Maluku, Bangka Belitung Islands, and West Nusa Tenggara) as much as 0.48 million tons. The decline in cassava production occurs due to a decrease in harvested area 53.58 thousand hectares (34%) and productivity by 4.04 quintal / hectare (1.73%) (Outlook Cassava, 2016).

Bangka Belitung is one of the cassava production centers outside Java and Bangka Regency is one of the cassava-producing regions with the largest harvested area (520 ha) in Bangka Belitung. However, the area harvested is not in accordance with production in 2015 as much as 1,314 tons when compared with the West Bangka regency which has the result of production of 12 910 tons with an area of 505 ha harvest. Conditions cassava production in Bangka are contradictory or inversely proportional to the results of the analysis of the national cassava (Kementan, 2016), where the national cassava production decline in 2015 due to a decrease in harvested area.

Improvement on cassava production required by Bangka Regency to adjust the crop area by analyzing the commodity cassava from upstream to downstream. If Bangka could increase cassava production, it will directly affect both the market offers local and national markets. The impact of increased local cassava deals in Bangka Regency followed good marketing activities will affect the demand for local cassava Bangka.

From the demand side, there are several factors that affect demand are: (1) The increasing number of people who are interested in plants cassava varieties of elephant as the successful impact of persuasive government accompanied by the emergence of a processing plant cassava or also called factory of Tapioca in Riausilip District, Kenanga District and The largest factory in Indonesia located in Puding Besar District (Bangka Pos, 2016), (2) The price level in the plant cassava, and (3) The price level of other tubers. In terms of deals, some of the factors that affect cassava, among others: (1) The rising trend cassava plantation area, (2) climate, (3) Prices of production facilities, and (4) Development of cassava technologies.

The development of cassava in Bangka based on increased harvested area and the processing plant cassava / tapioca ready to accommodate the results of the cassava community in small and large scale. Food crop cassava is one of the agricultural products which have the properties of easy maintenance and low cost. So based on the nature of the cassava, cassava productivity of food commodities need to get intensive treatment in post-harvest handling and marketing constraints, so the cassava to the factory or direct consumers are still in good condition and quality.

Bangka Regency is one of the cassava-producing areas in Bangka Belitung Province. Production of cassava production Bangka Regency has fairly low compared to other districts. Bangka Regency cassava currently can only be marketed in the traditional markets and small-scale local factory, this is due to cassava production Bangka Regency is not maximized.

The limited number of local factories are scattered in several District, to give effect to its important role in delivering business administration institute cassava farmers. Because if the farmers sell directly to end consumers, farmers will face risks in the form of transportation costs, the cost of workers' wages and limited market information that is generally only held by institutions of business administration. Changes in selling prices which occurred cassava farm level is also sufficient barometer fluctuated with the price of cassava in the province of Lampung. In 2016, the price of cassava in the province of Lampung is experiencing a decrease in prices due to imports of tapioca large enough (Kompas, 2016). That situation needs to be addressed by the Indonesian government to limit imports of tapioca starch quotas to protect domestic farm products.

One form of the efficient market is to use marketing system formed relatively short with the functions of equitable trading system. In addition, the characteristics of efficient markets is the distribution of margin trading system is spread evenly on all players in the trading system or institution and part of the price at the retail level received by farmers.